

Topic	Item	Checklist item description	Reported on Line
Title	1	The diagnosis or intervention of primary focus followed by the words “case report”	Title
Key Words	2	2 to 5 key words that identify diagnoses or interventions in this case report, including "case report"	Keywords
Abstract (no references)	3a	Introduction: What is unique about this case and what does it add to the scientific literature?	Abstract
	3b	Main symptoms and/or important clinical findings	Abstract
	3c	The main diagnoses, therapeutic interventions, and outcomes	Abstract
	3d	Conclusion—What is the main “take-away” lesson(s) from this case?	Abstract
Introduction	4	One or two paragraphs summarizing why this case is unique (may include references)	Introduction, L6
Patient Information	5a	De-identified patient specific information.	Case 1: L1. Case 2: L1
	5b	Primary concerns and symptoms of the patient.	Case 1: L4, 12. Case 2: L3
	5c	Medical, family, and psycho-social history including relevant genetic information	Case 1: L1. Case 2: L1
	5d	Relevant past interventions with outcomes	Case 1: L2. Case 2: L3
Clinical Findings	6	Describe significant physical examination (PE) and important clinical findings.	Case 1: L5, 13. Case 2: L4
Timeline	7	Historical and current information from this episode of care organized as a timeline	Case 1: L4, 12, 25. Case 2: L3, 13, 18
Diagnostic Assessment	8a	Diagnostic testing (such as PE, laboratory testing, imaging, surveys).	Case 1: L16, L26. Case 2: L8, 14, 19
	8b	Diagnostic challenges (such as access to testing, financial, or cultural)	N/A
	8c	Diagnosis (including other diagnoses considered)	Case 1: L22. Case 2: L15
	8d	Prognosis (such as staging in oncology) where applicable	Case 1: L30. Case 2: L23
Therapeutic Intervention	9a	Types of therapeutic intervention (such as pharmacologic, surgical, preventive, self-care)	Case 1: L33. Case 2: L25
	9b	Administration of therapeutic intervention (such as dosage, strength, duration)	Case 1: L33. Case 2: L25
	9c	Changes in therapeutic intervention (with rationale)	N/A
Follow-up and Outcomes	10a	Clinician and patient-assessed outcomes (if available)	Case 1: L25. Case 2: L30
	10b	Important follow-up diagnostic and other test results	Case 1: L30. Case 2: L35
	10c	Intervention adherence and tolerability (How was this assessed?)	Case 1: 34. Case 2: L30
	10d	Adverse and unanticipated events	N/A
Discussion	11a	A scientific discussion of the strengths AND limitations associated with this case report	N/A
	11b	Discussion of the relevant medical literature with references .	Discussion (All section)
	11c	The scientific rationale for any conclusions (including assessment of possible causes)	Discussion (All section)
	11d	The primary “take-away” lessons of this case report (without references) in a one paragraph conclusion	Discussion L74
Patient Perspective Informed Consent	12	The patient should share their perspective in one to two paragraphs on the treatment(s) they received	N/A
	13	Did the patient give informed consent? Please provide if requested	Yes ☒ No ☐